

PARTICIPATION OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IN PROTECTING THE ENVIRONMENT

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада глобал хавфсизликнинг таркибий қисми бўлган экологик хавфсизликни таъминлашга доир халқаро хужжатлар ва мазкур жараёнда Ўзбекистоннинг иштироки таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: глобал хавфсизлик, экологик хавфсизлик, халқаро экологик ташкилотлар, минтақавий ва глобал ҳамкорлик тенденциялари.

АННОТАЦИЯ В статье анализируются международные документы по обеспечению экологической безопасности, которая является составной частью глобальной безопасности, и участие Узбекистана в этом процессе.

Ключевые слова: глобальная безопасность, экологическая безопасность, международные экологические организации, тенденции регионального и глобального сотрудничества.

ABSTRACT The article analyzes international documents on ensuring environmental safety, which is an integral part of global security, and the participation of Uzbekistan in this process.

Key words: global security, environmental safety, international environmental organizations, trends in regional and global cooperation.

Introduction. Issues of global security tightening are noted by the world opinion as the main communication direction of various scientific circles, practical meetings, forums and other discussions. Conclusions and approaches arising from these discussions are unanimous. According to him, there are global threats and their elimination is beyond the scope of one region or one country. That is why they are given a global definition. Therefore, the elimination of existing risks in a particular field or system requires mutual integration, cooperation and a number of other factors. In addition, it is a self-evident fact that environmental problems that pose a global threat to humanity can be solved through international cooperation based on their scale and nature.

After gaining its independence, Uzbekistan began to pay special attention to issues of environmental protection among the problems to be solved. In particular, it should be noted that the attention to environmental security, which is an important direction of global security, has been increasing in recent years. This can be explained by the following factors:

- Aggravation of the environmental situation in the region and the world;
- Sharp reduction of water resources;
- Further intensification of the ecological crisis in the Aral region;

- Increase in consumption of natural resources;
- Land salinization and aggravation of natural climate changes;
- The risk of loss of biological diversity and other factors can be cited.

Among the main ways to change the current situation in a positive direction, to preserve the biosphere at least in its current state, attention to the situation at the government level, strengthening of the existing legislation and enforcement mechanisms, and, in turn, requires extensive cooperation with international organizations involved in the field. Therefore, Uzbekistan began to establish cooperative relations with international organizations from the first periods of the history of independent statehood. It is known that the United Nations Organization is the world's largest international organization in terms of the number of member states, geographical scope, and scope of influence. Our country became an equal member of this organization in 1992, and from that time began to actively participate in major UN projects. Among them, he became an important initiator and executor of global environmental protection projects.

It is known that the UN supports global projects related to maintaining peace, ensuring security, achieving mutual equality in international relations, and sustainable development, and leads these projects. Five of the six main bodies operate in the organization's headquarters in New York. Under his auspices, more than 10,000 resolutions aimed at making the world more stable were adopted, including more than 2,000 resolutions aimed at environmental protection and ensuring environmental safety in the world. Therefore, there is a need to dwell on the participation of Uzbekistan in major UN projects aimed at ensuring environmental stability.

Literature review. Uzbekistan's relations with the UN have been developing since 1993. In the same year, the representative office of the organization in Uzbekistan started working. "The UN Office is a structure that unites the UN's specialized agencies and program systems into a single state, and has the main goal of meeting the needs of countries, taking into account the priorities and goals put forward by governments" [1].

Our country occupies a special place in the activities of UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme), which is considered the "Environmental Program" of the United Nations. In particular, the participation of Uzbekistan in issues related to the elimination of environmental crises in Central Asia and the world is highly appreciated by the organization's leaders. This can be explained by the following factors:

First of all, Uzbekistan is becoming regular in tasks such as providing this organization with new information, proposing regional and global mechanisms for identifying and eliminating problems, in the context of the sharp derailment of the environment in the world;

Secondly, the trends of supporting UNEP projects in issues such as environmental safety, widespread use of environmentally friendly production methods are reflected in government programs and projects;

Thirdly, at the international conference, forum and other scientific-practical conferences held at the initiative of the organization, the participation of the agencies responsible for the environmental situation operating in Uzbekistan, the national experience aimed at eliminating the existing problems is widely discussed on an international scale.

In particular, the fact that the environmental situation on the island and its shores is discussed within the framework of international organizations, and is accepted as one of the

permanent topics that are separately discussed at the meetings of the Central Asian countries in various formats, confirms our opinion.

Analysis of Uzbekistan's participation in international agreements aimed at environmental protection shows that today our country is not indifferent to international and regional activities related to environmental safety. At this point, it is worth mentioning some of the international documents that Uzbekistan has ratified and is implementing in its territory. On May 18, 1993, the Republic of Uzbekistan joined the Vienna Convention on the Protection of the Ozone Layer and the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer.

The "Vienna Convention" on the protection of the ozone layer is an international legal document aimed at ensuring international environmental security and reflects the general content of the agreements at the end of the conference held in Vienna, Austria in 1985. The peculiarity of this document is that it serves as a general standard for the protection of the Ozone layer. This document has been ratified by 197 countries and is considered as a means of determining practical actions.

One of the unique aspects of the Vienna Convention is that each country can develop its projects and programs in the field of environment and improve the legal framework. However, the legal framework to be developed cannot deviate from the UN Charter or the provisions of the Convention. Secondly, the practical actions of a particular state are intended to prevent harmful effects on other countries. This document, ratified by Uzbekistan, stipulates compliance with the following provisions:

- Determining the exact level of emissions released into the atmosphere by industrial enterprises at the international and regional level;
- development and implementation of specific measures and programs for the protection of the ozone layer adopted at the national and international level;
- work based on scientific, technical and other conclusions aimed at protecting the ozone layer from changes caused by human influence;
- introducing regularity in the activities of scientific centers that monitor changes in the ozone layer, ensuring regularity in the statistical review of data, conducting systematic observations that provide for taking appropriate measures when negative consequences are observed;
- involves making appropriate decisions and developing recommendations to prevent changes that are harmful to the atmosphere and human health.

Issues of international cooperation occupy a special place in the main provisions of the convention. According to him,

Issues such as the norms stipulated by the parties in their national legislation, assistance to developing countries directly or through authorized international bodies in the process of their implementation, development of technologies and knowledge occupy a special place. According to the convention, international cooperation is carried out in the following ways:

- a) Facilitating the purchase of alternative technologies for states;
- b) provide them with information and relevant instructions or other documents about alternative technologies and equipment;

s) delivery of necessary equipment and tools for conducting research and systematic observations;

d) extensive cooperation in training necessary scientific and technical personnel” [2].

According to the international experience of legislation, it is one of the natural processes that accepted legal documents lose their essence over time and cannot meet the requirements of a certain period. In this respect, it can be observed that the Vienna Convention has been modernized several times based on the demands of the new era. An early example of such a reality is the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer. The main content of the document is that, according to it, there are restrictions on the export and import of substances that destroy the ozone layer. In addition, Article 5 of the protocol requires developing countries to change their industries to substances and technologies that are safe for the ozone layer.

The London Amendment to the Convention specifies substances that can deplete the Ozone layer and envisages their phase-out by industry. The international summit hosted by the Danish city of Copenhagen on November 23-25, 1992 was a continuation of the Montreal Protocol, which is referred to in history as the Copenhagen Amendment. According to the amendment, it can be seen that the use of a number of elements and substances is prohibited. The next changes to the Montreal Protocol were made after the meeting held in Beijing, China, from November 29 to December 3, 1999. “The Beijing Amendment sets new levels of consumption in the activities of states, prohibits the trade of any substances with countries that have not ratified this amendment, and introduces specific forms for developing countries. The production of prohibited substances has been limited, and some articles of the protocol have been amended” [3].

The government of Uzbekistan has separately ratified the aforementioned legal documents, the Montreal Protocol, the London, Copenhagen and Beijing amendments. The Vienna Convention was ratified in 1993, the Montreal Protocol and the London and Copenhagen Amendments in 1998, and the Montreal and Beijing Amendments in 2006.

The next international legal document ratified by the government of Uzbekistan is the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UN FCCC), which obliges the industrialized countries of the world to pay attention to the problems of climate change and to apply appropriate measures and tools. This convention was adopted in 1992 at the international summit held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. Date of entry into force March 1994. One of the special features of the document is its changing and updating provisions. That is, it is intended to change and improve the convention based on the requirements and needs of the time at the “Climate Change” summits held annually by the countries that have ratified the convention. The annual summits are held in the form of a conference called the Conference of the Parties (COP).

One of the main causes of climate change is undoubtedly the rapid development of industry. The Conference of Parties to the Convention “COP” presents the problems that have developed over a period of time to the annual meeting and is responsible for developing new rules and negotiating obligations, in turn, making relevant decisions.

The first meeting of the Conference of Supporters of the Convention was held in 1995. The meeting was hosted by the German city of Berlin, where additional obligations related to climate protection were assigned to developed countries, and later this reality entered history under the name “Berlin Mandate”. The rules and obligations of the “Climate Change

Convention” are changing from year to year. For example, after the next conference held in Kyoto, Japan in December 1997, the provisions of the convention were slightly expanded. Its changing characteristics are mainly determined by a sharp reduction in emissions.

In 2007, the government of Uzbekistan ratified the international document “On measures for the implementation of investment projects within the framework of the Clean Development Mechanism” called the “Kyoto Protocol”. Based on the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 9 of January 10, 2007, a separate Regulation was developed, according to which: “The Regulation is applicable to the international market within the framework of the Clean Development Mechanism of the Kyoto Protocol by legal entities, regardless of the form of ownership, on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, attracting foreign investors. determines the procedure for the preparation and implementation of investment projects involving the purchase of certified emission reductions” [4].

Research Methodology. There is a need to consider Uzbekistan's aspiration to become an important subject of the international community in all directions on the example of some numbers. In particular, the statistics of the legal and practical reforms carried out in relation to ecological safety, which is the subject of our research, show the general state of these processes in our country. It is worth mentioning that until today the Republic of Uzbekistan has ratified about 300 international documents providing for environmental protection. Of course, joining these documents, on the one hand, imposes a certain responsibility on the country, and on the other hand, it allows promoting positive trends such as activity and initiative in the international arena. This approach was developed by Uzbek scientist B. Omonov explains as follows: “The integration of the international environmental policy of the states, the mutual harmony of the elements of the institutional system aimed at protecting national interests, is the basis for their globalization at the transnational level. In this case, two strategic directions are clearly visible, namely: the first is the development of national doctrines defining global strategic goals, integration into world political environmental processes, and the formation of the “architecture” of international environmental political relations, the second is the strategic goals and tasks of national security, the nature of international environmental policy and defining the fundamental sources and principles that determine the scope of tasks” [5].

Analysis and results. Uzbekistan's integration into the international environmental security space is important. This can be explained by the following factors:

First, our country has been experiencing an ecological crisis both regionally and globally in recent years. This is characterized by the difficult situation in the Aral Bay region, the situation with transboundary rivers and a number of other aspects;

Secondly, since one of the main means of realizing national interests is related to ensuring security, in this process environmental security, which is a component of national security, is seen as a reality directly related to the development of international relations;

Third, global problems cannot be solved by regional means. This is a fact that does not require proof. In this respect, Uzbekistan, as one of the countries experiencing the global environmental crisis, actively participates in the international arena with its own initiatives, one of the main demands of our time;

Fourth, the need to harmonize national and universal interests is directly related to the integration of global environmental interests, the unanimity of views on the environment; **Fifth**, achieving compatibility of international standards, general rules developed by the international community with national legislation and other regulatory legal documents will have a positive effect on the full functioning of the system;

Sixthly, opportunities such as the introduction of promising projects aimed at ensuring international environmental security into national practice, assimilation of directions suitable for regional characteristics, accelerate integration into the international community.

It should be said that the island problem remains one of the main issues of the new century as a global environmental problem. Therefore, in the speeches of the head of our state Sh. Mirziyoev on international platforms, one can often find conceptual views and calls for saving the island. In particular, on September 19, 2017, at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, the opinions about the decreasing level of the island from year to year mean that this issue remains a global problem for the 21st century. At the same time, the head of our state stated that “Uzbekistan supports the projects of conventions on the use of water resources of the Amudarya and Syrdarya basins developed by the UN Regional Center for Preventive Diplomacy” [6] against the background of the fact that the effective use of water resources in the region causes specific problems.

It is noteworthy that Uzbekistan regularly expresses its position on the most important regional and global issues and their solutions in order to become an important subject of world politics. In the context of the 2020 pandemic, the President of Uzbekistan also put forward a number of initiatives aimed at ensuring stability in the world at the 75th session of the UN General Assembly held online. Undoubtedly, environmental safety issues have a special place among these initiatives. In this session, the head of state again drew the attention of the international community to the situation in the Aral Bay region. The President's report contains the following points in this regard: “We propose to adopt a special resolution of the United Nations General Assembly on declaring the Aral Bay region as a region of ecological innovation and technology. It would be appropriate to celebrate the date of approval of this important document as the International Day of Protection and Restoration of Ecological Systems” [7].

In the regional and global format of environmental protection, Uzbekistan shows its activity in two important directions. The first is participation in international conferences and constructive initiatives of major forums aimed at ensuring environmental safety, and the second is offering their services aimed at stabilizing the environmental situation. In particular, at the next session of the UN General Assembly held on September 19, 2023, the President of Uzbekistan put forward a number of initiatives. Among them is his support for the establishment of the position of the UN Secretary-General's Special Representative for Water Resources, as well as his initiative to hold the Central Asia Climate Dialogue and the adoption of the resolution “Central Asia Facing Global Climate Threats: Solidarity for Common Prosperity”. On the other hand, our opinion is also confirmed by the offer of their services to host the “International Climate Forum” in Samarkand in 2024.

Conclusion/Recommendations. In conclusion, the participation of Uzbekistan in the activities of international environmental organizations in environmental protection ensures the national interests of the country. At the same time, it fully helps our country to become an equal subject of the international community. Therefore, the fulfillment of the obligations specified in the legal documents of the UN and other international organizations aimed at

ensuring environmental safety, participation in the adoption of new standards with their own initiatives will ensure the stabilization of the existing situation.

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